

THE TRANSMISSION LINE MATRIX METHOD

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Summary - The transmission line matrix method plays a crucial role in improving communication, electronics and remote sensing technologies. It enables the development of more efficient, reliable and advanced systems that have a positive impact on people's lives, making communication and access to information faster, efficient and accessible. It is essential for many technological innovations that benefit society as a whole.

Keywords: Matrix; technologies; development; communication; society.

INTRODUCTION

TLM is used to analyze and simulate electrical transmission systems. It is widely used in electrical engineering, telecommunications and electronics. The importance of TLM lies in its ability to accurately model the propagation of electromagnetic waves along complex transmission lines, considering effects of reflections, refractors, interferences and losses. It allows the analysis of various phenomena, such as signal propagation in circuits, antennas and wave guides. A detailed methodology is essential to describe the process of implementing TLM, including mathematical equations and numerical resolution using algorithms.

DEVELOPMENT

The main reason for the creation of this method is to allow for a simplified and accurate representation of transmission lines in large-scale electrical systems.

It was developed by researchers and engineers in the field of microwave and telecommunications. The process involved theoretical foundations of electromagnetic theory, mathematical models, parameter formulation, calculation algorithms, and experimental validation. Based on Maxwell's equations and the theory of transmission lines, allowing the representation of the characteristics of electromagnetic propagation in transmissionlines. Even more refined and improved over time, with various variants and extensions proposed to deal with different cases and situations. Today, the transmission line matrix method is widely used in analysis and design of circuits and microwave systems.

The calculation of complex three-dimensional electromagnetic structures can contain various challenges due to various technical and computational difficulties, including geometric complexity: complex three dimensional structures may contain mixed geometries. Mesh size: Some structures require larger mesh, this leads to a significant increase in resource consumption. Non-linear behavior: this behaviour is of utmost importance, for example, for high-power optical devices, modeling this nonlinearity requires more complex equations.

This technique involves dividing the circuit into small segments and calculating the transmission relationships between them. TLM can be used to propagate sinusoidal waves, solve specific problems, and simulate the behavior of the circuit. It is commonly

used in high frequency devices and circuit designs, especially when considering propagation and reflection characteristics.

TABLE 1 – Some Software used for the application of TLM.

Software	Application	Language
CST Studio Suite	Simulate analyzing electromagnetism and microwaves	CST Script Language
Matlab	Create transmission line matrix models.	Matalab Language/ C++/ Java
DigSILENT PowerFacto ry	Simulate electrical power systems.	DigSILEN T Scripting Language.

Fig. 1. Code used to simulate the propagation of electromagnetic waves in transmission lines. [Octave, 2023].

Fig1 demonstrates the implementation of TLM in OCTAVE for simulation of electromagnetic wave propagation in transmission lines. This is a simple example of OCTAVE code that demonstrates how to implement the method to simulate the propagation of a wave on a one-dimensional transmission line. This method is a technique used in electrical and electronic engineering, it serves to analyze and design signal transmission systems, such as high-frequency transmission lines, coaxial cables, wave guides and other similar devices. Taking into account how it is used, one can raise some hypotheses to simplify the problem and allow an effective analysis. As mentioned some challenges above, we have listed some of their specifications:

1.Linearity: The system is assumed to be linear, which means that the relationship between tensions and currents is linear and satisfies the superposition. It allows linear analysis techniques to be applied.

2.Negligible losses: In most cases, the energy losses during the line are insignificant. However, in high-precision applications, these losses can be considerable.

3.Non-dispersion: In few cases, it is known that there is no wave dispersion, so the wave propagation speed does not vary with the frequency.

4.Suitable contour conditions are defined on the transmission line interfaces to reflect or transmit the waves according to the desired application.

Fig. 2. Non-Linear Circuit - an overview [Science Direct, 2023].

As can be seen in Fig. 2, one of the challenges mentioned, the analysis of nonlinearity in electrical circuits is an advanced process that involves the modeling of non-linearities by means of equations that describe how the circuit parameters vary with the amplitude of the signal. This method is commonly used for microwaves and high-frequency systems, where nonlinearities can be significant. The process involves modelling the nonlinearity present in the device or component, dividing the circuit into discrete segments, calculating the linear dispersion matrix for linear elements, introducing the non linearity in the calculation of the scatter matrix to non-linear elements and iterating the computation, process using numerical techniques. After the calculation of the dispersion matrix, the sinuses can be propagated throughout the circuit, considering the nonlinearities in each segment. The results can be analyzed to understand how nonlinearities affect system performance, including harmonic distortion, intermodulation, and compression effects. However, this analysis can be complex and requires solid knowledge of microwave theory and nonlinear device modelling. The use of circuit simulation tools and specialized software can greatly simplify the process.

Fig. 3. MCS Apex: Software used to analyze nonlinearity [Evotech, 2023].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After the study of the TLM, some of its properties were applied with the help of formulas such as the impedance transmission line, these are the

formulas for the calculation of impedance: impedance $Z = R$ or X_L or X_C ; impedance only in series $Z = \sqrt{(R^2 + X^2)}$; impedance only in Series $Z = (R + j(X - XC))$; resistance in any circuit = $R + jX$. From that, 5 exercises were done to calculate impedance. Thus, the results obtained are arranged in Table I.

Table I – Impedance calculation to be based on describing how the wave is reflected on the transmission line.

Test	Impedance
1	$80\Omega + j120\Omega$
2	$47.9 - j49.4\Omega$
3	9.9Ω
4	108Ω
5	18Ω

It is necessary to understand the reflection of a wave on a transmission line for several reasons, including energy efficiency, equipment protection, impedance matching, signal quality in communication systems, reduction of electromagnetic interference, security assurance and reliability in high voltage systems and design optimization. to meet specific requirements. This knowledge is essential for the design and operation of electrical and communication systems.

CONCLUSION

TLM provides an approximate solution for the propagation of electromagnetic waves through complex geometries. It shapes the two-dimensional space where the propagation of these waves occurs through a cartesian matrix of nodes.

It discretizes the wave propagation time and space and is an iterative method with two main propagation and connection processes.

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